

**Chaucer philosophe :
Philosophie, théologie et littérature en Angleterre à la fin du XIV^e siècle**

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Bibliographie thématique (très) sélective

1. TEXTES

Éditions et traductions

[En Anglais / Moyen-Anglais](#)

Riverside Chaucer, gen. ed. Larry D Benson (OUP, 2008)

[édition critique de référence de l'œuvre complète de Chaucer en Moyen-Anglais, avec notes explicatives]

Chaucer's Boece: A Critical Edition, based on Cambridge University Library, MS Ii.3.21, ff. 9r–180v, ed. Tim William Machan (Heidelberg, 2009)

[édition critique, avec notes textuelles mais sans notes explicatives]

Dream Visions and Other Poems, ed. Kathryn L. Lynch. *Norton Critical Editions* (Norton: 2006).

[édition d'étude du texte en Moyen Anglais de *Book of the Duchess*, *House of Fame*, *Parlement of Foules*, *Legend of Good Women*, et des poèmes brefs. Peu de notes explicatives, mais texte à l'orthographe simplifiée et traductions marginales de passages difficiles > plus 'reader-friendly' que le *Riverside Chaucer*...]

Chaucer's Dream Poems, ed Helen Phillips and Nick Havely. 2nd edition. London, 2015.

[édition d'étude du texte en Moyen Anglais de *Book of the Duchess*, *House of Fame*, *Parlement of Foules*, *Legend of Good Women*. Avec introductions et beaucoup de notes explicatives]

Troilus & Criseyde, ed. Stephen Barney. *Norton Critical Editions* (Norton: 2006).

[édition d'étude du texte en Moyen Anglais, avec texte en parallèle de la source principale de Chaucer, le Filostrato de Boccaccio, en traduction Anglaise moderne. Peu de notes explicatives, mais texte à l'orthographe simplifiée et traductions marginales de passages difficiles > plus 'reader-friendly' que le *Riverside Chaucer*...]

Canterbury Tales, translated into modern english by Neville Coghill (Penguin, 1952 and many reprints)

[traduction du texte en Anglais moderne ; version digitale disponible sur demande, auprès de Marco Nievergelt]

Traductions Françaises

Les contes de Canterbury et autres œuvres, trad. André Crépin et al. (Bouquins Éditions, 2010).

[traduction française des œuvres complètes de Chaucer]

Le Livre de la Duchesse et autres textes, texte bilingue, ed. et trad. Jonathan Fruoco (Classiques Garnier, 2021)

[édition bilingue, avec texte en Moyen-Anglais et traduction française de *Book of the Duchess, House of Fame, Parliament of Fowles*. Version électronique disponible en ligne sur Classiques Garnier Numérique]

2. ONLINE RESOURCES :

Chaucer Metapage :

<https://chaucermetapage.org/chaucer-resources/chaucer-pages/>

Chaucer Concordance :

<http://www.columbia.edu/~hfl2110/cconcord.html>

3. OUVRAGES GENERAUX

Chaucer : Biographie, Études Générales

- Akbari, Suzanne, and James Simpson, eds. *Oxford Handbook to Chaucer*. Oxford UP, 2021.
- Boitani, Piero, ed., *The Cambridge Companion to Chaucer*. Cambridge UP, 2003.
- Butterfield, Ardis, ed. *Chaucer and the City*. Cambridge: Cambridge, D. S. Brewer, 2006.
- Johnson, Ian, ed. *Geoffrey Chaucer in Context*. Cambridge University Press, 2019.
- Patterson, Lee. *Chaucer and the Subject of History*. Univ of Wisconsin Press, 1991.
- Pearsall, Derek. *The Life of Geoffrey Chaucer: A Critical Biography*. Oxford: Blackwell, 1992.
- Prendergast & Rosenfeld, *Chaucer and the Subversion of Form*. Cambridge UP 2018.
- Strohm, Paul. *Social Chaucer*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1989.
- Turner, Marion. *Chaucer: A European Life*. Princeton UP, 2019.

Contexte Historique, Social, et Intellectuel

- Catto, Jeremy I., and Ralph Evans. *The history of the University of Oxford. Vol. 2, Late medieval Oxford*. Oxford: Clarendon, 1992.
- Cole, Andrew. *Literature and Heresy in the Age of Chaucer*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2008.
- Courtenay, William J. *Schools & scholars in fourteenth-century England*. Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1987.
- Courtenay, William J. *Ockham and Ockhamism: Studies in the Dissemination and Impact of his Thought*. Leiden: Brill, 2008.

- Gelber, Hester. *It Could Have Been Otherwise: Contingency and Necessity in Dominican Theology at Oxford, 1300-1350*. Leiden: Brill, 2004.
- Hudson, Anne. *The Premature Reformation: Wycliffite Texts and Lollard History*. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1988.
- Kaye, Joel. *Economy and nature in the fourteenth century: money, market exchange, and the emergence of scientific thought*. Cambridge University Press, 2000
- Keen, Maurice Hugh. *England in the later Middle Ages: A Political History*. Routledge, 1973.
- Di Liscia, Daniel & Edith D. Sylla, eds. *Quantifying Aristotle: The Impact, Spread and Decline of the Calculatores Tradition*. Leiden: Brill, 2022
- Sylla, Edith D. *The Oxford Calculators and the Mathematics of Motion 1320–1350. Physics and Measurement by Latitudes* (New York: Garland Publishing, 1991 (PhD Thesis Harvard 1974).
- Tachau, Katherine. *Vision and Certitude in the Age of Ockham: Optics, Epistemology and the Foundation of Semantics, 1250–1345*. Leiden: Brill, 1988.

Savoir Universitaire et Littérature Vernaculaire en Angleterre

- Cannon, Christopher. *From Literacy to Literature: England, 1300-1400*. Oxford University Press, 2016.
- Cannon, Christopher. "The Middle English writer's schoolroom: Fourteenth-century English schoolbooks and their contents." *New Medieval Literatures* 11 (2009): 19-38
- Goldie, Matthew Boyd. *Scribes of Space: Place in Middle English Literature and Late Medieval Science*. Cornell University Press, 2019.
- Karnes, Michelle. *Imagination, Meditation, and Cognition in the Middle Ages*. University of Chicago Press, 2011
- Mann, Jill "‘He Knew Nat Catoun’: Medieval School-Texts and Middle English Literature", in Jill Mann and Maura Nolan, eds. *The Text in the Community: Essays on Medieval Works, Manuscripts, Authors, and Readers*. Notre Dame, Ind.: University of Notre Dame Press, 2006, pp. 41-74.
- Robertson, Kellie. *Nature Speaks: Medieval Literature and Aristotelian Natural Philosophy*. University of Pennsylvania Press 2016.
- Rosenfeld, Jessica. *Ethics and Enjoyment in Late Medieval Poetry: Love after Aristotle*. Cambridge UP, 2011.
- Wetherbee, Winthrop. 1975. "Some Intellectual Themes in Chaucer's Poetry." In *Geoffrey Chaucer*, edited by George D. Economou. New York: McGraw-Hill, pp. 75 – 91.

4. CHAUCER 'PHILOSOPHE'...

(NB : qualité souvent très variable... ouvrages rigoureux garantis présentés avec un *astérisque...)

- *Astell, Ann W. *Chaucer and the Universe of Learning*. Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press, 1996.
- *Baker, David P. "Numbered Possibilities: Chaucer and the Evolution of Late-Medieval Mathematics." *The Palgrave Handbook of Literature and Mathematics*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham, 2021. 23-40.
- Baker, David P. (2013) Literature, Logic and Mathematics in the Fourteenth Century, Durham theses, Durham University. Available at Durham E-Theses Online: <http://etheses.dur.ac.uk/7716/>

- * Bell, Jack Harding. *Chaucer and the Disconsolations of Philosophy: Boethius, Agency, and Literary Form in Late Medieval Literature*. Doctoral Thesis, Duke University. 2016. [HERE](#)
- *Bennett, J.A.W., *Chaucer at Cambridge and Oxford*. Oxford, Clarendon Press, 1974.
- Buchanan, Peter. *Contingent Chaucer: Experience, Time, and Modality in Chaucerian poetics*. Doctoral Thesis, University of Oxford, 2021. Available [HERE](#).
- *Burnley, J. D. "Chaucer's 'Termes'." *The Yearbook of English Studies* 7 (1977): 53-67.
- Cartlidge, Neil. "'Scientia vera'?" Holcot and Chaucer on Astrological Determinism, Magic, Talismans, and Omens." *the Chaucer review* 55.3 (2020): 279-297
- Cartlidge, Neil. "Ripples on the Water?: The Acoustics of Geoffrey Chaucer's House of Fame and the Influence of Robert Holcot." *Studies in the Age of Chaucer* 39.1 (2017): 57-98.
- Collette, Carolyn P. *Species, Phantasms, and Images: Vision and Medieval Psychology in the Canterbury Tales*. University of Michigan Press, 2001.
- * Courtenay, William J. "The Dialectic of Divine Omnipotence in the Age of Chaucer: A Reconsideration." *Nominalism and Literary Discourse*. Brill, 1997. 111-121
- Delaney, Sheila. *Chaucer's 'House of fame': The poetics of skeptical fideism*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1972.
- Delasanta, Rodney 'Chaucer and Strode', *Chaucer Review* 25.2 (1991), 205–18.
- Gabrovsky, Alexander N., *Chaucer the Alchemist*. Palgrave Macmillan, New York, 2015
- Hirsh, John C. "A Scotian Reading of the Man of Law's Tale and the Clerk's Tale." *The Modern Language Review* 116.1 (2021): 1-14.
- Keiper, Hugo, Richard J. Utz, and Christoph Bode *Nominalism and Literary Discourse: New Perspectives*. Amsterdam and Atlanta: Rodopi, 1997.
- Lynch, Kathryn L. *Chaucer's Philosophical Visions*. Cambridge: Boydell & Brewer, 2000.
- Michelet, Fabienne, and Martin Pickhavé, 'Philosophy, Logic, and Nominalism', in Suzanne Akbari and James Simpson, eds. *Oxford Handbook to Chaucer*.
- * Miller, Mark. *Philosophical Chaucer: Love, Sex and Agency in the Canterbury Tales*. Cambridge UP, 2004.
- * Minnis, Alastair (2009). 'Looking for a Sign: the Quest for Nominalism in Ricardian Poetry', in his *Translations of Authority in Medieval English Literature: Valuing the Vernacular*. Cambridge UP, 2009, pp. 38–67.
- Olson, Glending. "Snub and White; Chaucer, Logic, and Strode." *Journal of English and Germanic Philology* 117.2 (2018): 185-211
- Peck, Russell A. (1978) 'Chaucer and the Nominalist Question', *Speculum* 53.4 (1978), 745–60.
- *Penn, Stephen. 'Literary Nominalism and Medieval Sign Theory', in Christoph Bode, Hugo Keiper, and Richard J. Utz, *Nominalism and Literary Discourse: New Perspectives*. Amsterdam: Rodopi, 1997, pp. 157–90.
- *Robertson, Kellie. *Nature Speaks: Medieval Literature and Aristotelian Natural Philosophy*. University of Pennsylvania Press 2016. (Chapter 5 on Chaucer)
- Roney, Lois (1990). *Chaucer's 'Knight's Tale' and Scholastic Psychology*. Tampa: University of South Florida Press, 1990.
- *Rosenfeld, Jessica. *Ethics and Enjoyment in Late Medieval Poetry: Love after Aristotle*. Cambridge UP, 2011. (Chapters 3, 4, and 5 on Chaucer)
- Utz, Richard J. ed. *Literary Nominalism and the Theory of Rereading Late medieval Texts: A New Research Paradigm*. Lewiston, N.Y.: Edwin Mellen, 1995
- Watts, William H. (1997) 'Chaucer's Clerks and the Value of Philosophy.'" In *Nominalism and Literary Discourse: New Perspectives*, edited by Hugo Keiper, Richard J. Utz, and Christoph Bode, 145-55. Amsterdam: Rodopi, 1997.

- Williams, David. 'Distentio, Intentio, Attentio: Intentionality and Chaucer's Third Eye,' *Florilegium* 15 (1998): 37–59.
- *Zeeman, Nicolette (2014). "Philosophy in Parts: Jean de Meun, Chaucer and Lydgate", *Uncertain Knowledge: Scepticism, Relativism and Doubt in the Middle Ages*, ed. Dallas G. Denery II, Kantik Ghosh and Nicolette Zeeman. Turnhout: Brepols, 2014, 213-34.

5. ŒUVRES 'mineures' DE CHAUCER

NB : les références sont limitées aux contributions qui examinent la dimension spécifiquement philosophique de l'œuvre de Chaucer.

5.a Boece et l'influence de la *Consolation*

>> A synoptic edition of Boethius (allowing users to read the original side by side with multiple translations into different languages, including Jean de Meun's French Translation and Chaucer's English *Boece*), is available online : Boethius: *De consolatioe Philosophiae*, Bibliotheca Polyglotta Graeca et Latina, University of Oslo,

<https://www2.hf.uio.no/polyglotta/index.php?page=volume&vid=216>

- Bell, Jack Harding. *Chaucer and the Disconsolations of Philosophy: Boethius, Agency, and Literary Form in Late Medieval Literature*. Doctoral Thesis, Duke University. 2016. (ch. 1) [HERE](#)
- Hoenen, Marten, and Lodi Nauta, eds., *Boethius in the Middle Ages: Latin & Vernacular Traditions of the Consolatio Philosophiae, Studien und Texte zur Geistesgeschichte des Mittelalters, No. LVIII*. Leiden: Brill, 1997
- Johnson, Eleanor. *Practicing Literary Theory in the Middle Ages: Ethics and the Mixed Form in Chaucer, Gower, Usk, and Hoccleve*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013. (sur l'influence du *prosimetrum* de Boèce sur l'éthique et l'esthétique de Chaucer).
- Minnis, Alastair. "Aspects of the Medieval French and English Traditions of the 'De Consolatioe Philosophiae'." In Margaret Gibson, ed. *Boethius: His Life, Thought and Influence*. Oxford: Basil Blackwell, 1981, pp. 312-61.
- Minnis, Alastair J., ed. *Chaucer's Boece and the medieval tradition of Boethius*. Vol. 18. Boydell & Brewer, 1993.
- Murton, Megan. "Boethius and Chaucer." *Carmina Philosophiae* 25 (2016): 1-24
- Quinn, William A. "Chaucer, Arguing "in good feyth"." *English Studies* 102.4 (2021): 395-414

5.b *Le Roman de la Rose* : Influence sur Chaucer et traduction

- Dahlberg, Charles. (1999). *The Romaunt of the Rose: A Variorum Edition of the Works of Geoffrey Chaucer*. Vol. 7. Norman: University of Oklahoma Press, 1999.
- Diekstra, F.N.M (1988). 'Chaucer and the Romance of the Rose' *English Studies* 69 (1988): 12–26.
- Knox, Philip. *The Romance of the Rose and the Making of Fourteenth-Century English Literature*. Oxford University Press, 2022.
- Finlayson, John (1990). "'The 'Roman de la Rose' and Chaucer's Narrators.2" *Chaucer Review* 24 (1990): 187-210.
- Geltner, G. 'Faux Semblants: Antifraternalism Reconsidered in Jean de Meun and Chaucer'. *Studies in Philology* 101 (2004): 357-81.

- Minnis, Alastair (1997), "'A leur fez cousines': Words, Deeds, and Proper Speech in Jean de Meun and Chaucer.", in Masahiko Kanno *et al.*, eds. *Medieval Heritage: Essays in Honour of Tadahiro Ikegami* (Tokyo: Yushodo, 1997), pp. 31-63.
- Wallace, David. 'Chaucer and the European 'Rose'.' In Paul Strohm and Thomas J. Heffernan, eds., *Studies in the Age of Chaucer*, Proceedings, No. 1, 1984 (Knoxville, Tenn.: New Chaucer Society, 1985), pp. 61-67.

LES VISIONS

- Boitani, Pietro. "Old books brought to life in dreams: the Book of the Duchess, the House of Fame, the Parliament of Fowls." *The Cambridge Companion to Chaucer*. Cambridge UP 2003, pp. 58-77.
- Minnis, Alistair, with V. J. Scattergood and J. J. Smith, *Oxford Guides to Chaucer: The Shorter Poems*. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1995.
- Wasserman, Julian. "Chaucer, Language, and the Early Dream Visions." *Interpretations* (1985): 31-52.

5.c *Book of the Duchess*

- Carruthers, Mary. "'The Mystery of the Bed Chamber': Mnemotechnique and Vision in Chaucer's Book of the Duchess" in John M Hill and D/M Sinnreich-Levi, eds., *Rhetorical Poetics the Middle Ages*. Cranbury, NJ: Fairleigh Dickinson University Press; London: Associated University Presses. 2000, pp. 67-87
- Fumo, Jamie C. (ed.), *Chaucer's Book of the Duchess: Contexts and Interpretations*. Cambridge: Brewer, 2018.
- Kiser, Lisa J., 'Sleep, Dreams, and Poetry in Chaucer's *Book of the Duchess*', *Papers on Language and Literature* 19 (1983), 3–12
- Rosenfeld, Jessica. *Ethics and Enjoyment in Late Medieval Poetry: Love after Aristotle*. Cambridge UP, 2011. Ch 3.
- Peter Travis, "White," *Studies in the Age of Chaucer* 22 (2000): 1–66.

5.d *House of Fame*

- Delaney, Sheila (1973). "'Ars Simia Naturae' and Chaucer's 'House of Fame'." *English Language Notes* 11 (1973): 1-5.
- Eldredge, Laurence. "CHAUCER'S" HOUS OF FAME" AND THE" VIA MODERNA"." *Neuphilologische Mitteilungen* 71.1 (1970): 105-119
- Gabrovsky, Alexander N. "Thought Experiments in Geoffrey's Dream: The Poetics of Motus Localis, Measurement, and Relativity in the House of Fame." *Chaucer the Alchemist*. Palgrave Macmillan, New York, 2015. 27-64.
- Goldie, *Scribes of Space: Place in Middle English Literature and Late Medieval Science*, ch. 6
- Irvine, Martin. "Medieval Grammatical Theory and Chaucer's House of Fame." *Speculum* 60.4 (1985): 850-76
- Nelson, Ingrid. 'Ambient Media and Chaucer's House of Fame' *English Literary History (ELH)*, 88.3 (2021), 551-78

5.e *Parlement of Foules*

- Cooney, Helen. "The" Parlement of Foules": A Theodicy of Love." *The Chaucer Review* 32.4 (1998): 339-376.
- Gabrovsky, Alexander N., 'Counterfactual Conditionals in the Avian Debate: *Ars Obligatoria* and Possible Worlds Semantics in the *Parliament of Fowls*', in *ibid.*, *Chaucer the Alchemist*. Palgrave Macmillan, New York, 2015, pp 201-24.
- Morgan, Gerald. "Chaucer's Adaptation of Boccaccio's 'Temple Venus in 'The Parliament of Fowls.'" *The Review of English Studies* 56.223 (2005): 1-36.
- Olson, Paul A. "The Parlement of Foules: Aristotle's Politics and the Foundations of Human Society." *Studies in the Age of Chaucer* 2.1 (1980): 53-69.
- Powrie, Sarah. "Knowing and Willing in Chaucer's Parliament of Fowls." *The Chaucer Review* 50.3-4 (2015): 368-392
- Powrie, Sarah. "A Moral Garden "Out of Olde Feldes": Deallegorized Virtue in Chaucer's Parliament of Fowls." *Modern Philology* 114.2 (2016): 170-194.
- Reed, Thomas L. (1980). 'Chaucer's "Parlement of Foules": The Debate Tradition and the Aesthetics of Irresolution.' *Revue de l'Universite d'Ottawa* 50 (1980): 215-22.

5.f Legend of Good Women

- Collette, Carolyn P. *Rethinking Chaucer's Legend of Good Women*. Boydell & Brewer Ltd, 2014. (Chapter 3)
- Delany, Sheila. *The Naked Text: Chaucer's Legend of Good Women*. Univ of California Press, 1994
- Goldie, *Scribes of Space: Place in Middle English Literature and Late Medieval Science*, ch 8.
- McCormick, Betsy, et al. *The Legend of Good Women: Context and Reception*. No. 36. DS Brewer, 2006.

6. TROILUS & CRISEYDE

- Bell, Jack Harding. *Chaucer and the Disconsolations of Philosophy: Boethius, Agency, and Literary Form in Late Medieval Literature*. Doctoral Thesis, Duke University. 2016. [HERE](#)
- Buchanan, Peter. "Reading bodies, books, and beyond: experience and contingency in *Troilus and Criseyde*." *Textual Practice* (2021): 1-21
- Carruthers, Mary. 'Virtue, Intention, and the Mind's Eye in T&C'
- Cook, Alexandra. "'O swete harm so queynte": Loving Pagan Antiquity in *Troilus and Criseyde* and the Knight's Tale." *English Studies* 91.1 (2010): 26-41.
- Heinrichs, Katherie. "'Lovers' Consolations of Philosophy" in Boccaccio, Machaut, and Chaucer." *Studies in the Age of Chaucer* 11.1 (1989): 93-11
- Mann, Jill. "Chance and Destiny in *Troilus and Criseyde* and the Knight's Tale." In Piero Boitani, ed., *The Cambridge Companion to Chaucer*. Cambridge UP, 2003, pp. 93-111
- Reichl, Karl. 'Chaucer's *Troilus*: Philosophy and Language', in Boitani, *The European Tragedy of Troilus*.
- Rosenfeld, Jessica. *Ethics and Enjoyment in Late Medieval Poetry: Love after Aristotle*. Cambridge UP, 2011. Ch 5.
- Sarah B. Rude, Eye Beams and Boethian Sufficiency in T&C

- Wetherbee, Winthrop. *Chaucer and the poets: An essay on Troilus and Criseyde*. Cornell University Press, 1984/ 2016.

7. CANTERBURY TALES

Kolve, V. A. *Chaucer and the Imagery of Narrative: The First Five Canterbury Tales*. Stanford, Calif.: Stanford University Press, 1984.

Tasioulas, Jacqueline. "DYING OF IMAGINATION IN THE FIRST FRAGMENT OF THE " CANTERBURY TALES"." *Medium Ævum* 82.2 (2013), 213-35.

Wimsatt, James I. "John Duns Scotus, Charles Sanders Peirce, and Chaucer's Portrayal of the Canterbury Pilgrims." *Speculum* 71.3 (1996): 633-645.

7.a *Knight's Tale*.

- Finlayson, John. "The " Knight's Tale": The Dialogue of Romance, Epic, and Philosophy." *The Chaucer Review* (1992): 126-149.
- Guidry, Marc S. "The Parliaments of Gods and Men in the " Knight's Tale"." *The Chaucer Review* 43.2 (2008): 140-170
- Mann, Jill. "Chance and Destiny in 'Troilus and Criseyde and the Knight's Tale.'" In Piero Boitani, *The Cambridge Companion to Chaucer*. Cambridge, 2003, pp. 93-111.
- Minnis, Alastair. *Chaucer and Pagan Antiquity*. Brewer, 1981.
- Roney, Lois (1990). *Chaucer's 'Knight's Tale' and Scholastic Psychology*. Tampa: University of South Florida Press, 1990
- Ruggiers, Paul G. "Some philosophical aspects of 'The Knight's Tale.'" *College English* 19.7 (1958): 296-302

7.b *Miller's Tale*

- Bishop, Louise M. "" Of Goddes pryvetee nor of his wyf": Confusion of Orifices in Chaucer's Miller's Tale." *Texas Studies in Literature and Language* 44.3 (2002): 231-246
- Blamires, Alcuin. "Philosophical Sleaze? The 'strok of thought' in the Miller's Tale and Chaucerian Fabliau." *Modern Language Review* 102.3 (2007): 621-640
- Johnston, Andrew James. "The exegetics of laughter: Religious parody in Chaucer's Miller's Tale." *A History of English Laughter*. Brill, 2002. 17-33
- Newhauser, Richard, and Michael Raby. "Curious Labor in the Miller's Tale." *ELH* 86.1 (2019): 1-25.
- Watts, William H. "Chaucer's Clerks and the Value of Philosophy." *Nominalism and Literary Discourse*. Brill, 1997. 145-155

7.c *Reeve's Tale*

- Yaeger, Susan. "A Whit Thyng in Hir Ye": Perception and Error in the " Reeve's Tale." *The Chaucer Review* (1994): 393-404
- Watts, William H. "Chaucer's Clerks and the Value of Philosophy." *Nominalism and Literary Discourse*. Brill, 1997. 145-155

- Woods, William F. "Symkyn's Place in the" Reeve's Tale"." *The Chaucer Review* 39.1 (2004): 17-42.

7.d *Merchant's Tale*

- Fyler, John M. "Hateful Contraries in 'The Merchant's Tale'." *Critical Survey* 30.2 (2018): 20-50
- Jones, Mike Rodman. "January's Genesis: Biblical Exegesis and Chaucer's Merchant's Tale." *Leeds Studies in English*(2008): 53-87
- Kohler, Michelle. "Vision, Logic, and the Comic Production of Reality in the" Merchant's Tale" and Two French Fabliaux." *The Chaucer Review* 39.2 (2004): 137-150
- Schroeder (Carruthers), Mary C. "Fantasy in the" Merchant's Tale"." *Criticism* 12.3 (1970): 167-179.
- Walling, Amanda. "Placebo Effects: Flattery and Antifeminism in Chaucer's Merchant's Tale and the Tale of Melibee." *Studies in Philology* 115.1 (2018): 1-24

7.e *Nun's Priest's Tale*

- Jager, Eric (1990). 'Croesus and Chauntecleer: The Royal Road of Dreams', *Modern Language Quarterly* 49 (1990): 3-18.
- Payne, F. Anne. 1976. "Foreknowledge and Free Will: Three Theories in the Nun's Priest's Tale." *Chaucer Review* 10, no. 3: 201 – 19
- Travis, Peter W. "The Nun's Priest's Tale as Grammar-School Primer." *Studies in the Age of Chaucer* 1984.1 (1984): 81-91
- Travis, Peter. *Disseminal Chaucer: Rereading the Nun's Priest Tale*. Notre Dame, IN: University of Notre Dame Press, 2010
- Wheatley, Edward. 'Commentary Displacing Text: "The Nun's Priest's Tale" and the Scholastic Fable Tradition.' *Studies in the Age of Chaucer* 18 (1996): 119-41.

7.f *Summoner's Tale*

- Hasenfratz, Robert (1996). 'The Science of Flatulence: Possible Sources for the Summoner's Tale', *Chaucer Review* 30 (1996), 241–61
- Olson, Glending, "Measuring the Immeasurable: Farting, Geometry, and Theology in the Summoner's Tale", *Chaucer Review* 43 (2009), 414-27.
- RD Perry
- Pratt, Robert A. "Albertus Magnus and the Problem of Sound and Odor in *the Summoner's Tale*," *Philological Quarterly* 57 (1978): 267–68.
- Travis, and Peter "Thirteen Ways of Listening to a Fart: Noise in Chaucer's *Summoner's Tale*," *Exemplaria* 16 (2004): 323–48.

7.g *Pardoner's Tale*

- Lavinsky, David. "Turned to Fables: Efficacy, Form, and Literary Making in the Pardoner's Tale." *The Chaucer Review* 50.3-4 (2015): 442-464
- Minnis, Alastair. *Fallible Authors/ Chaucer's Pardoner and Wife of Bath*. University of Pennsylvania Press, 2013.

- Patterson, Lee. "Chaucer's Pardoner on the couch: Psyche and Clio in medieval literary studies." *Speculum* 76.3 (2001): 638-680.
- Vance, Eugene. "Chaucer's Pardoner: Relics, Discourse, and Frames of Propriety." *New Literary History* 20.3 (1989): 723-745